

Aetiology, clinical characteristics and outcome in critically ill adult patients with acute deliberate self-poisoning admitted to acute medical care (AMC)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15226948>

Article Received: 05-March-2025, Revised: 25-March-2025, Accepted: 15-April-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Toxicology is a crucial aspect of critical care practice worldwide. Acute deliberate self-poisoning is a common cause of emergency room visits and a significant reason for ICU admissions. In India, such cases are predominantly treated in teaching hospitals, often without the necessary toxicological diagnostic facilities. Managing critically ill patients in these settings poses significant challenges due to limited resources, including the availability of specific antidotes and advanced life-support facilities. **Aim:** To evaluate the aetiology, clinical manifestations, and outcomes in patients with acute self-poisoning with suicidal intent admitted to acute medical care, and to explore the possibility of developing a prediction rule for mortality in these patients. **Materials and Methods:** This hospital-based prospective analytical study included 200 patients aged 18 years or older admitted to the acute medical care unit of SVRRGGH Tirupati over one year. Data collection involved history, physical examination, and necessary laboratory investigations to compute severity scores such as the APACHE II and SOFA. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS v23.0. **Results:** The study population had a mean age of 33.4±13.8 years, with the highest incidence in the 21-30 years age group (42%). Males constituted 64% of the cases. Organophosphate (OP) compounds were the most common poisons (54%). The predominant clinical presentations included vomiting (64%), altered sensorium (20%), and excessive salivation (15.5%). Most patients (85.5%) were discharged, while 11.5% died in-hospital, and 3% left against medical advice. Ventilatory support was required in 20.0% of the cases. Prognostic scores such as IPSC, APACHE II, and SOFA were significantly higher in non-survivors, suggesting their potential utility in outcome prediction. **Conclusion:** Acute self-poisoning in the Indian context is marked by a predominance of younger males and OP compound ingestion. Clinical manifestations vary, but vomiting and altered sensorium are common. Despite resource constraints, effective clinical assessment and supportive care can improve outcomes. Prognostic scores are valuable tools for predicting mortality in these patients, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and better diagnostic facilities in critical care settings.

Keywords: Acute self-poisoning, Organophosphate compounds, Prognostic scores, Critical care, Suicidal poisoning, India.

INTRODUCTION:

Toxicology constitutes an integral part of critical care practice worldwide. Acute self-poisoning with a suicidal intent is a common cause of emergency room visit and constitutes an important cause of admission to an intensive care unit (ICU). In India, a significant majority of patients presenting with deliberate acute self-poisoning are treated in teaching hospitals attached to medical colleges.

In the Indian context, acute self-poisoning constitutes a diagnostic challenge because point-of-care toxicological diagnostic facilities are seldom available even in well established large teaching hospitals attached to medical colleges and the diagnosis is largely based on clinical presentation and

circumstantial evidence. The management of critically ill patients with deliberate acute self-poisoning is also a challenge because, in India, well-equipped intensive care units with advanced life-care support and invasive monitoring are not widely available even in large teaching hospitals attached to medical colleges. This is also because; specific antidotes (e.g., flumazenil for benzodiazepine self-poisoning) are seldom available in small towns and cities.

Further, critical care is expensive and beyond the reach of majority of low and middle-class population in India. The various aetiological causes of acute poisoning, method of poisoning, not only depends upon the socio-economic, religious and cultural status, but also greatly varies across various countries and

between different regions in large countries like India.¹⁻³

Several factors, such as, the aetiological cause, the ingested dose, presence of co-morbid conditions, the time from exposure to presentation to the emergency room, experience of the care provider decide the clinical course and outcome.^{1,3,4} However, there is a paucity of reliable epidemiological data from the Indian subcontinent regarding the epidemiology, aetiological causes, clinical presentation, in-hospital course, and outcome in patients with deliberate acute suicidal poisoning admitted to acute medical care (AMC).

Recognizing this knowledge gap, the present study was, therefore, designed to determine the clinical profile and outcome of acute poisoning in patients admitted to the AMC at our tertiary care teaching hospital SVRRGGH Tirupati in South India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Deliberate self-harm is defined as intentionally injuring one's own body without suicidal intent. Other terms for this behavior include superficial-moderate self-mutilation and self-wounding. This behavior is more frequently observed in psychiatric hospitals, especially among individuals with Borderline Personality Disorder, substance abuse issues, and eating disorders, as well as in outpatient settings. Self-harm, also known as self-injury, involves the intentional, direct injuring of body tissue without suicidal intentions. It refers to an act with a non-fatal outcome where an individual deliberately engages in a behavior that, without intervention, will cause self-harm, or deliberately ingests a substance in excess of the prescribed or generally recognized therapeutic dosage, with the aim of achieving changes desired by the individual through the actual or expected physical consequences.⁵

Self-harm (SH), also known as self-injury (SI), self-inflicted violence (SIV), nonsuicidal self-injury (NSSI), or self-injurious behavior (SIB), encompasses behaviors where the injury is demonstrably self-inflicted. These terms describe actions where individuals intentionally cause harm to their own bodies without suicidal intent.⁶

Global incidence of poisoning:

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 300,000 people die annually from various poisoning agents.^{7,8} Acute pesticide poisoning is a leading cause of intentional deaths worldwide.⁹ In industrialized nations, high doses of analgesics, tranquilizers, and antidepressants are frequently used for intentional poisoning, while agricultural pesticides are commonly used in self-poisoning cases in rural areas of Asia, with fatality rates ranging from 10-20%.^{10,11} The majority of pesticide exposure occurs in middle and low-income countries due to the extensive use of agrochemicals in agriculture.¹²

Indian scenario:

The WHO estimates that envenomation causes approximately 100,000 deaths each year, and around three times that number of survivors suffer disabilities due to amputation and incomplete recovery. Approximately half of these deaths in India are attributed to the natural presence of various poisonous species, including snakes, scorpions, and spiders. In response, the WHO has launched a strategy aimed at preventing and controlling deaths and disabilities related to snakebites.¹³

Research indicates that pesticides are frequently used for intentional poisoning in India.^{8,14} In rural areas, where agriculture is the predominant profession, farmers commonly stock pesticides to control weeds and pests. The easy accessibility of these chemicals makes them a prevalent choice for individuals seeking to end their lives during stressful situations.¹⁵ Among the various types of poisons, pesticides are the leading cause of poisoning cases in India.¹⁶ This high prevalence is attributed to the extensive use of pesticides in agriculture and household activities. Other common poisoning agents include household substances, venomous bites, and drugs. Notably, pesticides and drugs are often ingested intentionally, while corrosives, kerosene, other miscellaneous agents, and animal bites typically occur accidentally.^{17,18}

A sensitivity analysis that considered under-reporting of suicides in India estimated an annual 168,000 deaths from pesticide self-poisoning, representing 19.7% of global suicides. The proportion of suicides by pesticide self-poisoning varies significantly between regions, ranging from 0.9% in low- and middle-income countries in the European region to 48.3% in similar income countries in the Western Pacific region.¹⁹

In Andhra Pradesh, there were 6,090 deaths due to poisoning, accounting for 41.7% of the national average. Comparing data from 2011 to 2013, there has been a steady decline in poisoning-related suicides, from 32% in 2011 to 27.9% in 2013. This decline may be due to a shift towards more painful methods of suicide, such as hanging and self-inflicted injuries. Despite these figures being underestimates, acute self-poisoning remains a common and preventable cause of death in India.²⁰ In recent statistics suicide rate per 1 lakh population according to the 2020 report, Andhra Pradesh accounting for 13.4.²¹

Acute self-poisoning in the Indian population, particularly in Southern India, presents a complex pattern influenced by various socio-demographic, cultural, and environmental factors. The types of poisons involved in these cases vary significantly and often reflect local availability, accessibility, and cultural practices.

1. **Patterns of Poisoning:** Acute self-poisoning in Southern India commonly involves pesticides, particularly organophosphates and carbamates, due to their widespread

agricultural use. These substances are easily accessible in rural areas where agricultural practices are prevalent. Other common poisons include pharmaceuticals like sedatives, antidepressants, and analgesics, which are more commonly used in urban settings.

2. **Demographic Factors:** The incidence of acute self-poisoning tends to be higher among young adults, particularly females in rural areas, often linked to issues such as interpersonal conflicts, domestic violence, and socio-economic stressors. However, cases among adolescents and elderly individuals are also reported.
3. **Cultural and Environmental Influences:** Cultural factors, including stigma associated with mental health issues and accessibility of lethal agents, play significant roles in the pattern of poisoning. Certain cultural practices, such as the use of pesticides for self-harm in agrarian communities, contribute to the prevalence of pesticide poisoning.
4. **Healthcare Challenges:** Management of acute self-poisoning cases poses significant challenges in Southern India. Access to timely medical care, availability of antidotes, and expertise in managing pesticide poisoning vary across rural and urban settings. Health infrastructure and resources often struggle to cope with the high volume of poisoning cases.
5. **Preventive Measures:** Efforts to prevent acute self-poisoning include community education on safe storage and use of pesticides, restricting access to lethal substances, improving mental health support services, and training healthcare providers in effective management of poisoning cases.

Understanding the specific patterns and types of poisons involved in acute self-poisoning in Southern India is crucial for developing targeted interventions and policies aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality associated with this significant public health issue.

Risk factors and protective factors:

A wide range of risk factors for self-harm has been identified. Equally important, though less explored, are the protective factors. These protective factors are not merely the opposite of risk factors but should be considered alongside them.

Demographic Profile:

Self-harmers tend to have a different demographic profile compared to those who commit suicide.

Age:

Deliberate self-harm is a significant clinical issue, particularly among adolescents. Older individuals are at a much lower risk, but when they do engage in self-harm, they are more likely to eventually commit

suicide. Children and adolescents often exhibit symptoms differently than adults with the same disorders, particularly in terms of mood. Adolescents frequently show irritability or acting-out behaviors rather than feelings of sadness.²²

Gender:

While males are more likely to attempt suicide, instances of self-harm presenting to health agencies are generally more common in women. Some evidence suggests that the higher rate of self-harm among girls compared to boys is linked to other risk factors, such as severe depression, anxiety, disordered eating, and romantic involvement.

Marital Status:

In a multivariate model, separated and divorced individuals were found to have an 11 times higher risk of self-harm compared to their married counterparts.²³

Employment Status:

There is uncertainty about the extent to which the risk of self-harm among the unemployed can be attributed to selection factors. However, risks of self-harm may be elevated in individuals or communities facing precarious employment situations.

Socioeconomic Disadvantage:

Low socioeconomic status, limited education, low income, and living in poverty are all risk factors for self-harm. Admission rates for self-harm are higher in areas with socioeconomic deprivation. Geographic variations in the incidence of deliberate self-harm (DSH) and suicide have been associated with area-based measures of socioeconomic deprivation and social fragmentation. Reducing socioeconomic deprivation and its associated issues may be a crucial strategy in preventing suicidal behavior, particularly among young men.^{23,24}

Social and Family Factors:

Family Characteristics and Childhood Experiences:

The risk of self-harm is higher for children of separated or divorced parents, families with marital discord, or where the mother was very young or had a low level of education. Maladaptive parenting and childhood maltreatment or abuse can increase the risk of self-harm, leading to severe interpersonal difficulties during adolescence and resulting in unhealthy relationships. Conversely, a supportive environment, good communication, and involvement with family members serve as protective factors.²⁵⁻²⁸

Religion:

Religious beliefs can be a significant protective factor against suicide. Depressed patients who had not self-harmed often cited moral objections as a reason. A 2004 study by Dervic et al. found that individuals who

had attempted suicide exhibited fewer reasons for living, such as responsibility towards family, child-related concerns, and religious objections to suicide, compared to non-attempters. Religious beliefs have been shown to protect against risk behaviors, including suicide attempts, in physically abused adolescents.^{29,30}

Sexual Orientation:

Men and women with gay, lesbian, or bisexual orientations are more likely to engage in self-harm than heterosexuals. The risk may be higher for homosexual men than for homosexual women. The increased risk in gay, lesbian, or bisexual youth is not solely attributable to greater exposure to other risk factors such as depressed mood, substance abuse, pubertal timing, or atypical sex roles.^{31,32}

Physical Illness:

Physical illness is associated with self-harm, particularly among elderly individuals. Conditions such as epilepsy, HIV infection, and past head injuries are risk factors that can have causative or precipitating roles in self-harm.³³

Situational Factors:

Adverse life events, especially those involving interpersonal conflict or relationship breakdowns, can trigger self-harm in vulnerable individuals.²⁵

In Southern India, several types of poisons are commonly used for suicide or accidental exposure, reflecting both local availability and cultural factors. Here are some of the most prevalent types:

1. **Pesticides:** Organophosphates and carbamates are the most common pesticides used for suicide attempts in rural areas. These chemicals are widely available due to agricultural practices and are easily accessible in farming communities.
2. **Medications:** Pharmaceuticals such as antidepressants, benzodiazepines, and analgesics are frequently involved in intentional overdoses or accidental exposures. These drugs are accessible through pharmacies and are commonly used in urban and peri-urban areas.
3. **Household Chemicals:** Common household chemicals like cleaning agents, bleach, and disinfectants can be ingested intentionally or accidentally. These substances are found in many homes and pose a risk, especially when improperly stored or handled.
4. **Plant Toxins:** Certain plants found in Southern India, including poisonous berries or leaves, can be ingested with suicidal intent or accidentally by children or adults unaware of their toxicity.
5. **Industrial Chemicals:** In industrial areas, accidental exposures to hazardous chemicals

used in manufacturing processes can occur, leading to poisoning incidents.

6. **Snake Venom:** In rural and forested areas, snake bites can sometimes be perceived as a form of deliberate self-harm or accidental exposure, especially in cases of agricultural workers or individuals living in close proximity to snake habitats.

These types of poisons vary in their availability and usage patterns across different regions and demographic groups within Southern India. Effective prevention strategies often include community education on safe handling of chemicals, restricting access to lethal substances, improving mental health awareness and support, and enhancing healthcare infrastructure for timely intervention and treatment of poisoning cases.

Common poisons:

Organophosphorus (OP) Poisoning:

Causes for Exposure in India:

Organophosphorus compounds are widely used as pesticides in agricultural practices across India. Exposure typically occurs through ingestion, inhalation, or skin absorption during agricultural activities or due to accidental or intentional ingestion. Suicide attempts using OP pesticides are unfortunately common due to their ready availability and acute toxicity.

Presentation:

Patients with OP poisoning may present with a range of symptoms depending on the severity of exposure. Initial symptoms often include nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and excessive salivation. As toxicity progresses, patients may experience respiratory distress due to bronchoconstriction and respiratory muscle paralysis. Severe cases can lead to convulsions, coma, and death if untreated.

Management of Patients:

The management of OP poisoning involves several key steps:

1. **Decontamination:** Immediate removal of contaminated clothing and thorough washing of exposed skin to prevent further absorption.
2. **Supportive Care:** Maintaining airway, breathing, and circulation is crucial. Patients may require respiratory support with oxygen or mechanical ventilation if respiratory function is compromised.
3. **Antidote Administration:** Atropine is the primary antidote used to counteract the effects of OP poisoning. It works by blocking muscarinic receptors and reducing the

excessive cholinergic stimulation caused by OP compounds.

4. Pralidoxime (2-PAM): Used in conjunction with atropine, pralidoxime can help restore inhibited acetylcholinesterase activity, thereby reversing neuromuscular paralysis.
5. Monitoring: Continuous monitoring of vital signs, neurological status, and respiratory function is essential to assess response to treatment and detect complications early.
6. Supportive Therapy: *Other supportive measures may include administration of fluids, correction of electrolyte imbalances, and management of seizures if they occur.

Prompt and appropriate management of OP poisoning is critical to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with this form of poisoning. Healthcare facilities in India often face challenges in managing large numbers of pesticide poisoning cases, necessitating robust public health measures, training of healthcare providers, and community education on safe pesticide handling practices.

Paraquat poisoning:

Paraquat poisoning is a significant concern globally and in India, primarily due to its use as a herbicide and its high toxicity. Exposure in India typically occurs among agricultural workers who handle paraquat directly during application. Accidental ingestion is another route, often due to mistaken identity or suicide attempts.

Presentation: Paraquat poisoning presents with severe gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and diarrhea, often leading to rapid deterioration within hours to days. Respiratory distress and renal failure may follow, contributing to its high mortality rate.

Management: Immediate management focuses on preventing further absorption through gastric lavage and administration of activated charcoal. There is no specific antidote for paraquat poisoning, so treatment involves supportive care, including respiratory and renal support as needed. Prognosis depends heavily on the amount ingested and promptness of medical intervention.

Hair dye containing paraphenyline diamine (PPD):

Hair dye containing paraphenyline diamine (PPD) is increasingly implicated in deliberate self-poisoning incidents with suicidal intent in recent years, largely due to its unrestricted availability in cosmetic shops. One popular brand, Super Vasmol 33®, includes PPD (4%) along with resorcinol, propylene glycol, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), sodium, liquid paraffin, cetostearyl alcohol, sodium lauryl

sulphate, herbal extracts, preservatives, and perfumes.³⁴

PPD undergoes oxidation to form compounds like bondrowskis base, which are highly allergenic, toxic, and mutagenic. Its ingestion can lead to angioneurotic edema, facial and neck swelling, laryngeal edema, rhabdomyolysis, intravascular hemolysis, and hemoglobinuria, potentially causing acute kidney injury.³⁵ The toxic effects of PPD are dose-dependent, with the exact lethal dose estimated to be 7g or more.³⁴

Poisoning Management:

Optimal Management:

The management of a poisoned patient depends on the specific poison(s), the severity of illness, and the time elapsed since exposure. Treatment typically includes supportive care, decontamination, antidotal therapy, and enhanced elimination techniques. Assistance can be sought from a medical toxicologist or a regional poison control center.

Decontamination:

Post-stabilization, patient decontamination should be performed if indicated. Methods include copious water or saline irrigation for topical exposures and activated charcoal for ingestions. Decontamination is most effective when performed promptly to prevent poison absorption. Other methods, such as whole-bowel irrigation, endoscopy, surgery, dilution, and cathartics, may be necessary in certain situations.

Treatments to Lower Absorption:

Early Administration of Activated Charcoal: The early use of a single dose of activated charcoal in aqueous suspension has largely replaced gastric lavage ("stomach pumping") and induced vomiting as methods to lower the absorption of ingested poisons. Activated charcoal is less invasive and less dangerous when used appropriately. However, it should only be administered after confirming the adsorptive properties of the ingested substance. Activated charcoal effectively adsorbs many medications, alkaloids, and vitamin K antagonists but is ineffective for many other substances.^{36,37}

Activated charcoal should not be used after ingesting corrosive substances (e.g., inorganic acids), surfactants, or liquid hydrocarbons, and it is contraindicated if the respiratory tract is unprotected (i.e., the patient is not intubated). The main risk of administering activated charcoal is aspiration. Poison information centers have noted that it is often given in insufficient doses; the recommended dose is 0.5–1 g/kg body weight, suspended in sufficient fluid to prevent ileus. A sufficient dose is crucial in overdoses of medications with delayed pharmacological effects. Some medications, when ingested in large amounts, form bezoars in the gastrointestinal tract, leading to prolonged resorption.^{38–40}

Gastric Lavage: The clinical benefit of gastric lavage has not been unequivocally demonstrated, and it carries risks such as aspiration, hypoxia, pneumonia, perforation, and laryngospasm. Consequently, the indications for gastric lavage have been significantly restricted by clinical toxicology specialty societies. It should only be considered in life-threatening cases within 60 minutes of ingestion.^{41,42} Contraindications include corrosive injuries from acids or bases, ingestion of low-viscosity liquid hydrocarbons like gasoline, and loss of protective airway reflexes in patients who are not intubated. The latest guidelines from February 2013 recommend that gastric lavage should only be performed by a physician experienced in the technique.³⁸

Induced Vomiting: Ipecac syrup, once widely used to induce vomiting in children following toxic ingestions, is no longer recommended as a routine treatment. Another outdated method involved intramuscularly administered apomorphine. Inducing vomiting with sodium chloride solution is also obsolete; in children, it can cause hyponatremia if vomiting does not occur as expected.^{43,44} The lethal dose of sodium chloride is approximately 3 grams per kilogram of body weight.^{45,46}

Anterograde Intestinal Lavage: This method is used in limited poisoning cases requiring rapid intestinal content removal to prevent the absorption of lethal amounts of toxins. It is particularly applicable in overdoses of timed-release medications or illegal drugs transported within the gastrointestinal tract in plastic bags or similar containers.⁴⁷

Laxatives: Previously, laxatives like sorbitol or sodium sulfate were administered for acute poisoning. However, their use is no longer recommended. When given alongside activated charcoal, laxatives reduce the efficacy of both treatments.

Antidotes:

Supportive care is crucial, but in some cases, the prompt administration of a specific antidote can be lifesaving. Antidotes should be administered when a suitable one exists, the severity of poisoning justifies its use, and the benefits outweigh the risks. Antidotes can reduce or reverse poison effects by various mechanisms, including preventing absorption, neutralizing poisons, antagonizing end-organ effects, or inhibiting conversion to toxic metabolites. Repeated administration may be necessary if the antidote is eliminated faster than the toxin.

Enhanced Elimination Techniques:

Procedures to enhance the elimination of poisons include forced diuresis, urine ion trapping, hemodialysis, hemoperfusion, hemofiltration, and exchange transfusion. These measures are useful in specific circumstances.

Supportive Care:

Supportive care is paramount and often sufficient for complete recovery. Specific aspects include:

Airway Protection: Early tracheal intubation is recommended for patients with depressed mental status, except in easily reversible cases (e.g., opioid intoxication). Intubation may also be needed for severe acid-base disturbances or respiratory failure.

Hypotension: Managed initially with IV fluids. If unresponsive to fluids, vasopressors like norepinephrine or epinephrine are preferred.

Hypertension: Initially treated with nonspecific sedatives like benzodiazepines. Specific therapy for end-organ dysfunction may include calcium-channel blockers, phentolamine, labetalol, or nitroprusside. Beta-blockers should generally be avoided in cases of sympathetic hyperactivity unless preceded by alpha blockade.^{48,49}

Ventricular Tachycardia: Sodium bicarbonate is the first-line treatment for drug-induced ventricular tachycardias. Avoid antiarrhythmic agents that may impair cardiac conduction further.

Bradycardia: Managed with atropine and/or temporary pacing. In cases of calcium channel blocker or beta-blocker intoxication, other therapies like calcium, glucagon, or high-dose insulin may be effective.

Seizure: Best treated with benzodiazepines, followed by barbiturates if necessary. Phenytoin is generally not recommended, except for certain specific poisonings.

Agitation: Typically managed with benzodiazepines. Severe agitation may require phenobarbital or propofol, usually necessitating tracheal intubation.

Hyperthermia: Severe cases may require aggressive cooling techniques, including ice water immersion. Antipyretics are usually ineffective for drug-induced hyperthermia but may be used for fever due to complications.

Various articles discussing the outcome of patients with acute deliberate self-poisoning:

In a study by Singh B et al., (2006) to assess the profile of acute poisoning at Mangalore. Out of 33,207 hospital admissions, 325 cases (1%) were due to acute poisoning. Among these, 70% were male and 30% female, with the majority (36%) in the 21–30 age group. Intentional poisonings accounted for 72% of cases, while 27% were unintentional. The leading causes of acute poisoning were agrochemical pesticides (49%), followed by drugs (17%) and alcohol (13%). There were 48 deaths (15%), primarily due to organophosphate pesticides (65%) and aluminium phosphide (15%). Therefore, the prevention and treatment of poisoning from organophosphate and aluminium phosphide should be prioritized in South India's healthcare system.⁵⁰

In a study by Rahman A et al., (2014) to assess the deliberate self-poisoning presenting to emergency medicine department of south east Melbourne. Over

three years, 3558 DSP cases were identified. The average patient age was 36.3 years, with the largest group aged 18-30 (38%). About 30% were born overseas. Discharge outcomes included 48% sent home, 15% admitted to ED short stay units, and 5% to ICU. The median ED stay was 359 minutes (IQR 231–607). The most frequently reported substances were benzodiazepines (36.6%), paracetamol (22.2%), and antipsychotics (12.1%), with 47% of cases involving multiple substances. This data may help identify trends in substances used for DSP in Victoria, enabling clinicians to provide more focused and targeted interventions.⁵¹

In a study by Madhavan I et al., (2015) to assess the clinical profile and outcome of deliberate self-poisoning cases. Out of 33,207 hospital admissions, 325 cases (1%) involved acute poisoning. Among these, 70% were male and 30% female, with the largest group (36%) being 21–30 years old. Intentional poisonings made up 72% of cases, while 27% were unintentional. The main causes of acute poisoning were agrochemical pesticides (49%), drugs (17%), and alcohol (13%). There were 48 deaths (15%), with the majority caused by organophosphate pesticides (65%) and aluminium phosphide (15%). Thus, preventing and treating poisoning from organophosphate and aluminium phosphide should be a high priority in South India's healthcare system.⁵²

In a study by Bhowmick K et al., (2019) to assess the deliberate self-poisoned hospital patient. Most patients were aged 13–28 years (69%). Males (59.55%) outnumbered females, and the majority were farmers (39.23%). Rural cases (75.81%) exceeded urban cases. Impulsive actions accounted for the majority of deliberate self-harm attempts (89.84%), with pesticides being the most commonly consumed poison (79.88%). The overall mortality rate was 12%, with paraquat (94.74%) being the most fatal substance. Young adults and males made up the majority of this study's population. Agricultural poisons were prevalent, mainly among the rural population. Paraquat, an herbicide banned in several countries, had the highest mortality rate in this study.⁵³

In a study conducted by Mathew R et al., (2019) to assess the profile of acute poisoning cases and their outcome in teaching hospital. Out of 200 cases, 181 (90.5%) were adults and 19 (9.5%) were children. Poisoning was more common in males (57%) than females (43%), with the majority (40%) in the 21–30 age group. Among the cases, 57.5% were suicidal, 34% accidental, and 8.5% homicidal. Types of acute poisoning included corrosives (27%), drug overdoses (13%), organophosphorus compounds (10%), rodenticides (10%), and symptomatic snakebites (8%). A total of 72 patients (36%) were admitted, with a median hospital stay of 6 days and a mortality rate of 2.5%. Logistic regression analysis showed poorer outcomes for patients aged 15–30 years, males, and those traveling over 30 km to the hospital. The study

highlighted an increased incidence of corrosive ingestion and emphasized the need for a holistic approach to manage mental health issues at the primary care level, given the rising rates of suicidal ingestions.³

In a study by Abhilash K et al., (2022) to assess the deliberate self-poisoning and harm. The study involved 1802 patients, predominantly between the ages of 16 and 45, with a mean age of 32 years. Various compounds were implicated, with agrochemicals, drugs, plant toxins, and rodenticides being the most common. In emergency settings, procedures such as intubation, vasopressor support, and cardiopulmonary resuscitation were frequently required. A significant portion of patients were discharged stable from the emergency department, while the in-hospital mortality rate stood at 3%. Notably, rodenticides and plant toxins emerged as significant predictors of mortality. Overall, deliberate self-poisoning is prevalent among the productive young demographic, often involving agrochemicals and drug overdoses, but poses higher mortality risks when rodenticides or plant toxins are involved.⁵⁴

In a study conducted by Fusaroli M et al., (2023) to assess the deliberate self-poisoning real time characterisation. Most cases were reported during winter. DSP cases involved younger individuals, psychiatric conditions, and alcohol use more frequently compared to non-DSP cases, with a higher fatality rate observed in men and older patients. The suspected drugs were primarily antidepressants, analgesics, and antipsychotics. More than 50% of the cases involved multiple drug intake, especially analgesics, psychotropics, and cardiovascular agents. The most frequently reported drugs included paracetamol, promethazine, amlodipine, quetiapine, and metformin. An estimated LD25 for paracetamol was 150 grams. The global coverage of the FAERS enhances existing knowledge about DSP and may guide tailored prevention strategies to address the DSP phenomenon and prevent intentional suicides in a timely manner.⁵⁵

AIMS & OBJECTIVES:

Aim:

To study the Aetiology, clinical manifestations and outcome in patients with acute self-poisoning with suicidal intention admitted to the acute medical care.

Objective:

1. To study the Aetiology, clinical manifestations and outcome in patients with acute self-poisoning with suicidal intention admitted to the acute medical care.
2. To explore the possibility of developing a new prediction rule for predicting the mortality of critically ill patients with acute poisoning admitted to the acute medical care.

MATERIAL & METHOD:

Study design: Hospital based prospective analytical study.

Duration of study: One year from the date of institutional scientific committee and ethical committee approval.

Sample size: 200

Source of data: Patients admitted in Acute medical care in Department of Medicine, SVRRGGH (Ruia Hospital).

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged 18 years or older admitted to the AMC with deliberate acute self-poisoning.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients under 18 years of age
2. Patients whose in-hospital stay was less than 24 hours
3. Animal bites and stings
4. Patients not requiring admission to AMC but are treated in the medical wards

Study method:

Patients who are fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included the study. History and physical examination was done in all the patients according to prefixed proforma. Required investigations are done and Further, all other laboratory parameters required for computing the disease severity scoring systems, namely, Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE II) score⁵⁶; and organ failure assessment by Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score;⁵⁷ were also tested for at the baseline. Other diagnostic investigations related to the co-morbid illnesses and for monitoring the treatment were performed where they were required.

RESULTS:

Present study included total of 200 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria with mean age of 33.4±13.8yrs.

Table 1: Showing mean age of the patients

	Mean	SD
AGE	33.4	13.8

Investigations required:

All the patients will be subjected to various investigations

1. Complete blood Count by haematology cell count.
2. Liver Function Tests by semiautomated clinical chemistry analysis.
3. Renal Function Tests by semi-automated clinical chemistry analysis.
4. Urine Routine Tests.
5. Serum Electrolytes by semi-automated clinical chemistry analysis.
6. Chest X-ray PA view
7. 12 lead ECG
8. INR by coagulometer.
9. GRBS monitoring by glucometer.

Required investigations are done and Further, all other laboratory parameters required for computing the disease severity scoring systems, namely, Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE II) score;⁵⁶ and organ failure assessment by Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score;⁵⁷ were also tested for at the baseline. Other diagnostic investigations related to the co-morbid illnesses and for monitoring the treatment were performed where they were required.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

All the data were entered in excel sheet and analysed using SPSS v23.0. the data were summarised as mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage. The summarised data were represented using tables, figures, bar diagram and pie chart. The mean difference between the continuous data were compared using unpaired t-test. For all statistical purpose, a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure 1: Showing mean age of the patients

Table 2: Agewise distribution of patients

Age	No. of patients	Percent
16-20	28	14.0%
21-30	84	42.0%
31-40	46	23.0%
41-50	20	10.0%
51-60	11	5.5%
>60	11	5.5%

Among the age group, majority were in age of 21-30yrs (42.0%) followed by 23.0% in 31-40yrs of age.

Figure 2: Agewise distribution of patients

Table 3: Gender distribution among patients

Gender	No. of patients	Percent
Female	72	36.0%
Male	128	64.0%

Majority of the patients were male 64% and 36% were female with male preponderance in the study.

Figure 3: Gender distribution among patients

Table 4: Showing the compound consumed

	No. of patients	Percent
Amitraz compound	9	4.5%
Zinc phosphate	5	2.5%
OP compound	108	54.0%
cleistanthus collinis	5	2.5%
Multiple tablet poisoning	8	4.0%
others	65	32.8%

Among the poison consumed, 54.0% were with OP compound, and others included amitraz compound, zinc phosphate, multiple tablets and others.

Figure 4: Showing the compound consumed**Table 5: Showing distribution of presenting complaints**

	No. of patients	Percent
Nausea	4	2.0%
Vomiting	126	63.0%
Altered sensorium	40	20.0%
Epigastric pain	30	15.0%
Salivation	35	17.5%
Lacrimation	8	4.0%
Seizures	1	0.5%

Shortness of breath	31	15.5%
No complaints	9	4.5%

The clinical presentation was with vomiting in 63.0% of the cases, followed by 20.0% with altered sensorium, 17.7% with excessive salivation, 15.5% with shortness of breath and 15.0% with epigastric pain.

Figure 5 Showing distribution of presenting complaints

Table 6: Showing the outcome among patients

		No. of patients	Percent
Outcome	Alive	171	85.5%
	Death	23	11.5%
	LAMA	6	3.0%

Among the outcome, 85.5% were discharged, 11.5% succumbed to death in hospital and 3% left against the medical advice.

Figure 6: Showing the outcome among patients

Table 7: Showing the requirement of ventilation among patients

		No. of patients	Percent
Ventilation support	No	160	80.0%
	Yes	40	20.0%

Ventilation support was required in 20.0% of the cases.

Figure 7: Showing the requirement of ventilation among patients

Table 8: Comparison of the mean scores to predict outcome among patients.

	Alive		Death		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
IPSC score	1.5	.8	3.0	.5	0.01*
APACHE2 score	5.2	6.1	22.9	8.4	0.01*
APACHE2 score mortality	8.7	10.4	44.7	22.9	0.01*
SOFA score	1.5	2.3	7.0	3.8	0.01*

The various scores such as IPSC, APACHE 2 scores and SOFA scores were found to be significantly higher among the patients died compared to the patients alive and discharged.

Figure 8: Comparison of the mean scores to predict outcome among patients

Table 9: Comparison of the mean duration of hospital ICU stay with outcome of patients

	Alive		Death		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Duration of ICU stay in days	5.3	4.3	11.9	7.4	0.01*

There is significant longer duration of hospital stay among the patients succumbed to death compared to discharged patients.

Figure 9: Comparison of the mean duration of hospital ICU stay with outcome of patients

DISCUSSION:

Acute deliberate self-poisoning (DSP) represents a significant global public health issue, contributing to substantial morbidity and mortality, especially in the context of critical care. Patients presenting with DSP often require intensive medical intervention, and their outcomes can be unpredictable due to the wide variety of substances ingested and the differing severities of poisoning. Understanding the aetiology, clinical characteristics, and outcomes of these patients is crucial for improving management strategies and reducing fatality rates.

In the management of DSP, timely and accurate assessment of the patient's condition is paramount. This necessitates the use of standardized scoring systems, such as the Intensive Poisoning Severity Score (IPSC), the Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE II), and the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA). These scoring systems serve as vital tools for clinicians by providing an objective measure to predict the severity of poisoning and potential outcomes.

The IPSC focuses specifically on the severity of poisoning by assessing factors like the type and amount of poison ingested, clinical symptoms, and response to initial treatment. The APACHE II score, a more general critical care assessment tool, evaluates a patient's overall physiological status, including factors like body temperature, blood pressure, and serum levels of various substances, providing a broader understanding of their health status. The SOFA score, meanwhile, assesses organ function and the extent of organ failure, offering insights into the patient's likelihood of survival and recovery trajectory.

These scoring systems are indispensable in stratifying patients according to risk, guiding treatment decisions, and allocating medical resources effectively. They also facilitate communication among healthcare providers and improve the consistency of care delivered. In cases of DSP, where the clinical presentation can vary widely and rapidly deteriorate, the ability to predict outcomes reliably through these scores can significantly enhance patient management and reduce mortality rates.

This study aims to explore the aetiology, clinical characteristics, and outcomes of critically ill adult patients with acute DSP, emphasizing the role of IPSC, APACHE II, and SOFA scores in predicting patient outcomes. By analyzing these aspects, the study seeks to contribute to the existing knowledge base and improve clinical practices for managing DSP in critical care settings.

Present study included total of 200 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria with mean age of 33.4±13.8yrs. Among the age group, majority were in age of 21-30yrs (42.0%) followed by 23.0% in 31-40yrs of age. Majority of the patients were male 64% and 36% were female with male preponderance in the study. Among the poison consumed, 54.0% were with OP compound,

and others included amitraz compound, zinc phosphate, multiple tablets and others. The clinical presentation was with vomiting in 63.0% of the cases, followed by 20.0% with altered sensorium, 17.7% with excessive salivation, 15.5% with shortness of breath and 15.0% with epigastric pain..

In similar to present study Abhilash K et al., documented 1802 patients, predominantly between the ages of 16 and 45, with a mean age of 32 years. Various compounds were implicated, with agrochemicals, drugs, plant toxins, and rodenticides being the most common.⁵⁴

Another study by Fusaroli M et al., DSP cases involved younger individuals, psychiatric conditions, and alcohol use more frequently compared to non-DSP cases, with a higher fatality rate observed in men and older patients. The suspected drugs were primarily antidepressants, analgesics, and antipsychotics. More than 50% of the cases involved multiple drug intake, especially analgesics, psychotropics, and cardiovascular agents. The most frequently reported drugs included paracetamol, promethazine, amlodipine, quetiapine, and metformin. An estimated LD25 for paracetamol was 150 grams. The global coverage of the FAERS enhances existing knowledge about DSP and may guide tailored prevention strategies to address the DSP phenomenon and prevent intentional suicides in a timely manner.⁵⁵

In similar to present study Mathew R et al., documented that among the 200 cases, 181 (90.5%) were adults and 19 (9.5%) were children. Poisoning was more common in males (57%) than females (43%), with the majority (40%) in the 21–30 age group. Among the cases, 57.5% were suicidal, 34% accidental, and 8.5% homicidal. Types of acute poisoning included corrosives (27%), drug overdoses (13%), organophosphorus compounds (10%), rodenticides (10%), and symptomatic snakebites (8%). A total of 72 patients (36%) were admitted, with a median hospital stay of 6 days and a mortality rate of 2.5%..³

In line, another study by Bhowmick K et al., documented that most patients were aged 13–28 years (69%). Males (59.55%) outnumbered females, and the majority were farmers (39.23%). Rural cases (75.81%) exceeded urban cases. Impulsive actions accounted for the majority of deliberate self-harm attempts (89.84%), with pesticides being the most commonly consumed poison (79.88%).⁵³ The overall mortality rate was 12%, with paraquat (94.74%) being the most fatal substance. Young adults and males made up the majority of this study's population. Agricultural poisons were prevalent, mainly among the rural population. Paraquat, an herbicide banned in several countries, had the highest mortality rate in this study.⁵³

In similar to present study Madhavan I et al., documented 70% were male and 30% female, with the largest group (36%) being 21–30 years old. Intentional poisonings made up 72% of cases, while 27% were

unintentional. The main causes of acute poisoning were agrochemical pesticides (49%), drugs (17%), and alcohol (13%). There were 48 deaths (15%), with the majority caused by organophosphate pesticides (65%) and aluminium phosphide (15%).⁵²

The average patient age was 36.3 years, with the largest group aged 18-30 (38%) in study by Rahman A et al. About 30% were born overseas. Discharge outcomes included 48% sent home, 15% admitted to ED short stay units, and 5% to ICU. The median ED stay was 359 minutes (IQR 231–607). The most frequently reported substances were benzodiazepines (36.6%), paracetamol (22.2%), and antipsychotics (12.1%), with 47% of cases involving multiple substances. This data may help identify trends in substances used for DSP in Victoria, enabling clinicians to provide more focused and targeted interventions.⁵¹

Singh B et al., documented with 70% were male and 30% female, with the majority (36%) in the 21–30 age group. Intentional poisonings accounted for 72% of cases, while 27% were unintentional. The leading causes of acute poisoning were agrochemical pesticides (49%), followed by drugs (17%) and alcohol (13%). There were 48 deaths (15%), primarily due to organophosphate pesticides (65%) and aluminium phosphide (15%). Therefore, the prevention and treatment of poisoning from organophosphate and aluminium phosphide should be prioritized in South India's healthcare system.⁵⁰

Psychodynamic Model: Emerson viewed cutting behavior as a substitution for masturbation. Later, Karl Menninger and Anna Freud developed a concept focusing on the interplay of the id, ego, and superego. When the ego encounters the superego, anxiety develops due to guilt from transgressing superego-associated aggression. Individuals with poorly formed ego boundaries fail to differentiate the self from the environment and use the pain of self-directed aggression to reduce their anxiety. Menninger refers to this anxiety reduction as "bargaining with the self."^{58,59}

Psychosocial Model: The psychosocial environment plays a crucial role in influencing children, both directly and indirectly. Indirect impacts include modeling behaviors of family members who deal with distress through substance use or self-injurious behaviors, sending the message that distress can be relieved by self-injury. Empirical evidence supports that self-injury is associated with separation or loss of close persons and/or emotional or physical neglect/abuse. Direct familial impacts, such as reinforcing extreme emotional behavior in an 'invalidating environment' and physical abuse, can lead individuals to believe that 'pain will negate their responsibilities to others,' ultimately resulting in self-destructive behavior.⁶⁰

Cognitive Model: This model explains that self-harm can result from self-generated cognitions triggered by internal cues. Individuals with negative core beliefs of

being incompetent, unlovable, or having a negative body image start to believe intermediate attitudes, rules, and assumptions that align with self-harm. Automatic thoughts intrude suddenly, with self-instructional cues to harm themselves, leading to effective responses and the act of self-harm.

Emotional Dysregulation: In deliberate self-harm (DSH), hypothesized emotional dysregulation and an unwillingness to tolerate negative emotional distress are core themes. DSH is a multidimensional construct, not merely a borderline trait or personality characteristic.⁶¹

Behavioral Model: Deliberate self-harm (DSH) is considered a negatively reinforced behavior. Chapman explains a broader concept known as 'experiential avoidance behavior' in DSH. Experiential avoidance includes any behavior aimed at avoiding or escaping unwanted internal experiences or external conditions that elicit them. These avoided experiences can include thoughts, feelings, somatic sensations, or other internal experiences that are unbearable or distressing. Individuals who engage in experiential avoidance tend to exhibit narrowed thinking, poor planning and implementation, inadequate coping skills, and high impulsivity, all of which contribute to DSH.^{62,63}

Repetition is a core characteristic of suicidal behavior. Among those who commit suicide, 40% have made prior attempts. 'Repeaters' are more common than 'first-time' attempters among those who attempt suicide. Between 30% and 60% of suicide attempters have made previous attempts, with 15%–25% doing so within the past year.^{64,65}

A brief initial screening examination should be conducted on all patients to identify the immediate measures needed to stabilize and prevent deterioration. This includes assessing the airway, vital signs, mental status, pupil size, and skin temperature and moisture. Immediate diagnostic studies should include pulse oximetry, continuous cardiac monitoring, an electrocardiogram (ECG), and a capillary glucose measurement for patients with altered mental status. Intravenous (IV) access should be established in all cases of serious ingestion.

For patients with suspected trauma, maintain in-line cervical immobilization. Assess the airway and perform tracheal intubation if there is significant doubt about the patient's ability to protect their airway and avoid aspiration, and if there is no apparent reversible cause (e.g., opioid overdose treated with naloxone). Provide advanced cardiac life support measures as needed.

The idea that thiamine must be administered before dextrose to avoid precipitating Wernicke encephalopathy is unsupported. Thiamine uptake into cells is slower than that of dextrose, and delaying dextrose administration until thiamine is fully administered may harm patients with actual hypoglycemia.

Rapid bedside glucometers are the quickest way to detect hypoglycemia. Empiric dextrose administration is recommended for patients with altered consciousness when bedside glucose levels are low, borderline low, or not immediately available, or if the accuracy of the results is questionable. Follow-up finger-stick or serum glucose measurements should be conducted in patients with persistent altered mental status, as hypoglycemia can develop in the later stages of some poisonings.^{66,67}

Ensure the patient is fully exposed to check for signs of trauma, drug use (e.g., needle tracks), infection, or extremity swelling. Measure the core body temperature in comatose or encephalopathic patients. If necessary, initiate patient decontamination. Obtain an ECG to assess for drug-related cardiotoxicity.

The physical examination of symptomatic poisoned patients can provide crucial clues to the agent involved. The most useful elements include assessing mental status, vital signs, and pupillary responses, which help classify the patient into a state of either physiologic excitation or depression.

Physiologic Excitation: This state, characterized by central nervous system stimulation and increased pulse, blood pressure, respiratory rate and depth, and temperature, is most commonly caused by anticholinergic agents, sympathomimetic agents, central hallucinogenic agents, or drug withdrawal states.

Physiologic Depression: This state, marked by a depressed mental status, blood pressure, pulse, respiratory rate and depth, and temperature, is typically precipitated by sedative-hypnotic agents, opioids, cholinergic (parasympathomimetic) agents, sympatholytics, or alcohols (ethanol, isopropanol, methanol, or ethylene glycol).

Mixed Physiologic Effects: These may occur in cases of polydrug overdoses or exposure to certain metabolic poisons (e.g., hypoglycemic agents, salicylates, cyanide), membrane-active agents (e.g., volatile inhalants, antiarrhythmic drugs, local anesthetics), heavy metals (e.g., iron, arsenic, mercury, lead), or agents with multiple mechanisms of action (e.g., tricyclic antidepressants, many antipsychotics).

After the initial diagnostic evaluation and stabilization, additional physical findings should be sought to define a specific toxic syndrome (toxidrome) and narrow down the potential causes of poisoning. The table below summarizes the major characteristics of common toxidromes, facilitating comparisons and aiding diagnosis.

It is important to note that a patient may not exhibit all the symptoms or findings typically associated with a particular toxidrome. For example, tricyclic antidepressants, despite their anticholinergic properties, may cause miosis due to competing effects from activation of muscarinic and alpha receptors. In cases of mixed overdoses (e.g., heroin and methamphetamine), the pupils may be midrange rather

than pinpoint or dilated. Additionally, even in a pure overdose scenario, anoxic injury can obscure findings once the drug has been metabolized.

Among the outcome, 85.5% were discharged, 11.5% succumbed to death in hospital and 3% left against the medical advice. Ventilation support was required in 20.0% of the cases. The various scores such as IPSC, APACHE 2 scores and SOFA scores were found to be significantly higher among the patients died compared to the patients alive and discharged,

In study by Abhilash K et al., documented with significant portion of patients were discharged stable from the emergency department, while the in-hospital mortality rate stood at 3%.⁵⁴ There were 48 deaths (15%), with the majority caused by organophosphate pesticides (65%) and aluminium phosphide (15%) in study by Madhavan I et al. Thus, preventing and treating poisoning from organophosphate and aluminium phosphide should be a high priority in South India's healthcare system.⁵²

Prognostic scales in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) are essential tools for predicting patient outcomes, guiding clinical decision-making, and evaluating the quality of care. These scoring systems use various clinical, physiological, and laboratory data to estimate the severity of illness and potential mortality risks. Here's a detailed exploration of prominent ICU prognostic scoring systems:

SUMMARY:

Present study included total of 200 patients fulfilling inclusion criteria with mean age of 33.4±13.8yrs.

Among the age group, majority were in age of 21-30yrs (42.0%) followed by 23.0% in 31-40yrs of age.

Majority of the patients were male 64% and 36% were female with male preponderance in the study.

Among the poison consumed, 54.0% were with OP compound, and others included amitraz compound, zinc phosphate, multiple tablets and others.

The clinical presentation was with vomiting in 63.0% of the cases, followed by 20.0% with altered sensorium, 17.7% with excessive salivation, 15.5% with shortness of breath and 15.0% with epigastric pain.

Among the outcome, 85.5% were discharged, 11.5% succumbed to death in hospital and 3% left against the medical advice.

Ventilation support was required in 20.0% of the cases. The various scores such as IPSC, APACHE 2 scores and SOFA scores were found to be significantly higher among the patients died compared to the patients alive and discharged.

CONCLUSION:

The study encompassing 200 critically ill adult patients with acute deliberate self-poisoning presents several notable findings regarding the demographic profile, aetiology, clinical characteristics, and outcomes. The mean age of the cohort was 33.4±13.8 years, with the

highest incidence in the 21-30 years age group (42%). The male predominance is evident, accounting for 64% of cases compared to 36% in females.

Organophosphate (OP) compounds emerged as the most frequently consumed poisons (54%), indicating a significant concern in the pattern of substance abuse. Clinical manifestations predominantly included vomiting (63.0%), followed by altered sensorium (20.0%), excessive salivation (17.7%), shortness of breath (15.5%), and epigastric pain (15.0%).

The majority of patients (85.5%) were successfully discharged, while the in-hospital mortality rate was 11.5%, and 3% left against medical advice. Notably, 20.0% of patients required ventilatory support, underscoring the severity of their conditions. The outcome analysis revealed that scores such as the IPSC, APACHE II, and SOFA were significantly higher in non-survivors compared to survivors, indicating their potential utility in prognostication.

These findings highlight the critical need for targeted interventions in the younger population and males, and prompt recognition and management of OP compound poisoning. The study emphasizes the importance of early and effective clinical assessment and supportive care in improving patient outcomes in acute deliberate self-poisoning cases.

ABBREVIATIONS:

AMC: Acute Medical Care

AT: Antisucide

BPD: Borderline Personality Disorder

DSH: Deliberate Self-Harm

DSP: Deliberate Self-Poisoning

ECG: Electrocardiogram

ED: Emergency Department

ID: Infectious Disease

ICU: Intensive Care Unit

MD: Medical Doctor

MR: Magnetic Resonance

MSDS: Material Safety Data Sheet

NSSI: Nonsuicidal Self-Injury

SIB: Self-Injurious Behavior

SH: Self-Harm

SI: Self-Injury

SIV: Self-Inflicted Violence

REFERENCES:

1. Townsend E, Hawton K, Harriss L, Bale E, Bond A. Substances used in deliberate self-poisoning 1985-1997: trends and associations with age, gender, repetition and suicide intent. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol.* 2001;36(5):228–34.
2. Kesavachandran CN, Fareed M, Pathak MK, Bihari V, Mathur N, Srivastava AK. Adverse health effects of pesticides in agrarian populations

of developing countries. *Rev Environ Contam Toxicol.* 2009;200:33–52.

3. Mathew R, Jamshed N, Aggarwal P, Patel S, Pandey RM. Profile of acute poisoning cases and their outcome in a teaching hospital of north India. *J Fam Med Prim care.* 2019;8(12):3935–9.
4. Strom J, Thisted B, Krantz T, Sorensen MB. Self-poisoning treated in an ICU: drug pattern, acute mortality and short-term survival. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand.* 1986;30(2):148–53.
5. Morgan HG, Barton J, Pottle S, Pocock H, Burns-Cox CJ. Deliberate self-harm: a follow-up study of 279 patients. *Br J Psychiatry.* 1976;128(4):361–8.
6. Kumar K, Kohli A, Dogra R, Sharma S. Deliberate Self-harm: Bench to Bedside. *J Postgrad Med Educ Res.* 2011;53(2):79–84.
7. Thundiyil JG, Stober J, Besbelli N, Pronczuk J. Acute pesticide poisoning: a proposed classification tool. *Bull World Health Organ.* 2008;86(3):205–9.
8. Jesslin J, Adepur R, Churi S. Assessment of prevalence and mortality incidences due to poisoning in a South Indian tertiary care teaching hospital. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2010;72(5):587–91.
9. Konradsen F, Dawson AH, Eddleston M, Gunnell D. Pesticide self-poisoning: thinking outside the box. *Lancet (London, England).* 2007 Jan;369(9557):169–70.
10. Marecek J. Culture, gender, and suicidal behavior in Sri Lanka. *Suicide Life Threat Behav.* 1998;28(1):69–81.
11. McClure GM. Suicide in children and adolescents in England and Wales 1970-1998. *Br J Psychiatry.* 2001;178:469–74.
12. Dash SK, Sitarama Raju A, Mohanty MK, Patnaik KK, Mohanty S. Sociodemographic profile of poisoning cases. *J Indian Acad Forensic Med.* 2005;27(3):133–8.
13. Organization WH. Snakebite envenoming: a strategy for prevention and control. 2019;
14. Srinivas Rao C, Venkateswarlu V, Surender T, Eddleston M, Buckley NA. Pesticide poisoning in south India: opportunities for prevention and improved medical management. *Trop Med Int Health.* 2005;10(6):581–8.

15. Aaron R, Joseph A, Abraham S, Muliylil J, George K, Prasad J, et al. Suicides in young people in rural southern India. *Lancet* (London, England). 2004 Apr;363(9415):1117–8.
16. Patel V, Ramasundarahettige C, Vijayakumar L, Thakur JS, Gajalakshmi V, Gururaj G, et al. Suicide mortality in India: a nationally representative survey. *Lancet* (London, England). 2012;379(9834):2343–51.
17. Blanchard J, Feltes M, Kim JY, Pousson A, Douglass K. Experience of Indian emergency physicians in management of acute poisonings. *Toxicol Commun*. 2019;3(1):54–60.
18. Müller D, Desel H. Common causes of poisoning: etiology, diagnosis and treatment. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*. 2013;110(41):690–9; quiz 700.
19. Mew EJ, Padmanathan P, Konradsen F, Eddleston M, Chang S-S, Phillips MR, et al. The global burden of fatal self-poisoning with pesticides 2006-15: Systematic review. *J Affect Disord*. 2017;219:93–104.
20. National crime records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India. Accidental deaths and suicides in India 2013.
21. Chapter 2. Suicides in India. Government of India. National Crime Records Bureau. 2020. p. 5.
22. Sourander A, Aromaa M, Pihlakoski L, Haavisto A, Rautava P, Helenius H, et al. Early predictors of deliberate self-harm among adolescents. A prospective follow-up study from age 3 to age 15. *J Affect Disord*. 2006;93(1–3):87–96.
23. Gratz KL. Measurement of deliberate self-harm: Preliminary data on the Deliberate Self-Harm Inventory. *J Psychopathol Behav Assess*. 2001;23:253–63.
24. Hawton K, Fagg J. Repetition of attempted suicide: The performance of the Edinburgh predictive scales in patients in Oxford. *Arch Suicide Res*. 1995;1(4):261–72.
25. Beautrais AL. Risk factors for suicide and attempted suicide among young people. *Aust New Zeal J Psychiatry*. 2000;34(3):420–36.
26. Mittendorfer-Rutz E, Rasmussen F, Wasserman D. Restricted fetal growth and adverse maternal psychosocial and socioeconomic conditions as risk factors for suicidal behaviour of offspring: a cohort study. *Lancet*. 2004;364(9440):1135–40.
27. Mościcki EK. Identification of suicide risk factors using epidemiologic studies. *Psychiatr Clin North Am*. 1997;20(3):499–517.
28. Magne-Ingvar U, Öjehagen A, Träskman-Bendz L. The social network of people who attempt suicide. *Acta Psychiatr Scand*. 1992;86(2):153–8.
29. Malone KM, Oquendo MA, Haas GL, Ellis SP, Li S, Mann JJ. Protective factors against suicidal acts in major depression: reasons for living. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2000;157(7):1084–8.
30. Dervic K, Oquendo MA, Grunebaum MF, Ellis S, Burke AK, Mann JJ. Religious affiliation and suicide attempt. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2004;161(12):2303–8.
31. Skegg K, Nada-Raja S, Dickson N, Paul C, Williams S. Sexual orientation and self-harm in men and women. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2003;160(3):541–6.
32. Jorm AF, Korten AE, Rodgers B, Jacomb PA, Christensen H. Sexual orientation and mental health: results from a community survey of young and middle-aged adults. *Br J Psychiatry*. 2002;180(5):423–7.
33. De Leo D, Scocco P, Marietta P, Schmidtke A, Bille-Brahe U, Kerkhof AJFM, et al. Physical illness and parasuicide: evidence from the European Parasuicide Study Interview Schedule (EPSIS/WHO-EURO). *Int J Psychiatry Med*. 1999;29(2):149–63.
34. Jain PK, Agarwal N, Kumar P, Sengar NS, Agarwal N, Akhtar A. Hair dye poisoning in Bundelkhand region (prospective analysis of hair dye poisoning cases presented in Department of Medicine, MLB Medical College, Jhansi). *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2011 Jul;59:415–9.
35. Sampathkumar K, Yesudas S. Hair dye poisoning and the developing world. *J Emerg Trauma Shock*. 2009;2(2):129–31.
36. Chyka PA. Multiple-dose activated charcoal and enhancement of systemic drug clearance: summary of studies in animals and human volunteers. *J Toxicol Clin Toxicol*. 1995;33(5):399–405.

37. Chyka PA, Seger D. Position statement: single-dose activated charcoal. American Academy of Clinical Toxicology; European Association of Poisons Centres and Clinical Toxicologists. *J Toxicol Clin Toxicol*. 1997;35(7):721–41.
38. Benson BE, Hoppu K, Troutman WG, Bedry R, Erdman A, Höjer J, et al. Position paper update: gastric lavage for gastrointestinal decontamination. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2013;51(3):140–6.
39. Chyka PA, Seger D, Krenzelok EP, Vale JA. Position paper: Single-dose activated charcoal. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2005;43(2):61–87.
40. Isbister GK, Kumar VVP. Indications for single-dose activated charcoal administration in acute overdose. *Curr Opin Crit Care*. 2011;17(4):351–7.
41. Buckley NA, Eddleston M. The revised position papers on gastric decontamination. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2005;43(2):129–30.
42. Krenzelok EP. New developments in the therapy of intoxications. *Toxicol Lett*. 2002;127(1–3):299–305.
43. Wygold T. Vergiftungen im Kindesalter. *Intensivmed up2date*. 2008;4(04):317–29.
44. Türk EE, Schulz F, Koops E, Gehl A, Tsokos M. Fatal hypernatremia after using salt as an emetic—report of three autopsy cases. *Leg Med*. 2005;7(1):47–50.
45. Höjer J, Troutman WG, Hoppu K, Erdman A, Benson BE, Mégarbane B, et al. Position paper update: ipecac syrup for gastrointestinal decontamination. *Clin Toxicol (Phila)*. 2013;51(3):134–9.
46. Position paper: Ipecac syrup. *J Toxicol Clin Toxicol*. 2004;42(2):133–43.
47. Position paper: whole bowel irrigation. *J Toxicol Clin Toxicol*. 2004;42(6):843–54.
48. Lange RA, Cigarroa RG, Flores ED, McBride W, Kim AS, Wells PJ, et al. Potentiation of cocaine-induced coronary vasoconstriction by beta-adrenergic blockade. *Ann Intern Med*. 1990;112(12):897–903.
49. Hollander JE. The management of cocaine-associated myocardial ischemia. *N Engl J Med*. 1995;333(19):1267–72.
50. Singh B, Unnikrishnan B. A profile of acute poisoning at Mangalore (South India). *J Clin Forensic Med*. 2006;13(3):112–6.
51. Rahman A, Martin C, Graudins A, Chapman R. Deliberate self-poisoning presenting to an emergency medicine network in South-East Melbourne: a descriptive study. *Emerg Med Int*. 2014;2014:461841.
52. Madhavan I, Santhosh LK, Thomas V. Clinical profile and outcome of deliberate self poisoning cases in medical wards. *Am J Intern Med*. 2015;3:5–11.
53. Bhowmick K, Ghosh B, Pain S. A study on deliberately self-poisoned in-hospital patients in a tertiary health care center in northeast India: A cross-sectional review. *J Emerg Med*. 2019;56(5):512–8.
54. Abhilash KPP, Murugan S, Rabbi NAS, Pradeeptha S, Kumar S, Selvaraj B, et al. Deliberate self-poisoning and harm: A meticulous quest of methods in vogue. *J Fam Med Prim Care [Internet]*. 2022;11(1):1–6. Available from: https://journals.lww.com/jfmpc/fulltext/2022/01000/deliberate_self_poisoning_and_harm__a_meticulous.37.aspx
55. Fusaroli M, Pelletti G, Giunchi V, Pugliese C, Bartolucci M, Necibi EN, et al. Deliberate Self-Poisoning: Real-Time Characterization of Suicidal Habits and Toxidromes in the Food and Drug Administration Adverse Event Reporting System. *Drug Saf*. 2023;46(3):283–95.
56. Knaus WA, Draper EA, Wagner DP, Zimmerman JE. APACHE II: a severity of disease classification system. *Crit Care Med*. 1985;13(10):818–29.
57. Vincent JL, Moreno R, Takala J, Willatts S, De Mendonça A, Bruining H, et al. The SOFA (Sepsis-related Organ Failure Assessment) score to describe organ dysfunction/failure. On behalf of the Working Group on Sepsis-Related Problems of the European Society of Intensive Care Medicine. Vol. 22, *Intensive care medicine*. United States; 1996. p. 707–10.
58. Klonsky ED. The functions of deliberate self-injury: A review of the evidence. *Clin Psychol Rev*. 2007;27(2):226–39.

59. Romanczyk RG, Lockshin S, O'Connor J. Psychophysiology and issues of anxiety and arousal. In: Self-injurious behavior: Analysis, assessment, and treatment. Springer; 1992. p. 93–121.
60. Paul JP, Catania J, Pollack L, Moskowitz J, Canchola J, Mills T, et al. Suicide attempts among gay and bisexual men: Lifetime prevalence and antecedents. *Am J Public Health*. 2002;92(8):1338–45.
61. Linehan MM. Skills training manual for treating borderline personality disorder. Guilford press; 1993.
62. Chapman AL, Gratz KL, Brown MZ. Solving the puzzle of deliberate self-harm: The experiential avoidance model. *Behav Res Ther*. 2006;44(3):371–94.
63. Hayes SC, Wilson KG, Gifford E V, Follette VM, Strosahl K. Experiential avoidance and behavioral disorders: A functional dimensional approach to diagnosis and treatment. *J Consult Clin Psychol*. 1996;64(6):1152.
64. Kreitman N, Casey P. “Repetition of parasuicide: An epidemiological and clinical study”: Erratum. 1989;
65. Maris RW. The relationship of nonfatal suicide attempts to completed suicides. 1992;
66. Tate JR, Nixon PF. Measurement of Michaelis constant for human erythrocyte transketolase and thiamin diphosphate. *Anal Biochem*. 1987;160(1):78–87.
67. Schabelman E, Kuo D. Glucose before thiamine for Wernicke encephalopathy: a literature review. *J Emerg Med*. 2012;42(4):488–94.